

Issues of export of services in higher education institutions: the case of Bukhara region

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Abstract. The article discusses the features of choosing a strategy for exporting educational services for universities in the Bukhara region. The dynamics of the number of foreign students, the amount of income received from the export of educational services over the past decade have shown significant growth. A high proportion of foreign students studying in the country indicates the high competitiveness of the national education system. Export of educational services is an additional source of income for educational organizations. The location of the Bukhara region on the border with the countries of the Asia-Pacific region, which can be consumers of educational services, necessitates choosing a strategy for their export by universities in the region and studying possible proposals for the development of the learning process. The paper shows that education is a source of export income in the dynamically growing international market for these services, which is experiencing an intensification of competition between economically developed countries. The features of the growth of export of educational services by Russian universities are studied, restrictions are established that prevent the attraction of foreign students. The export of educational services by universities of the Bukhara region is studied, the shortcomings of the current strategies for the export of educational services by universities of the region are identified. Recommendations are offered for choosing a strategy for the export of educational services by universities of the Bukhara region. The system-forming principles of the strategy are proposed, taking into account regional and national capabilities. In conclusion, it is noted that the choice of the strategy of export of educational services will increase the competitiveness of universities in the Bukhara region and provide universities with additional income.

Key words: export of educational services, higher education, strategy, university, globalization.

Introduction.

The export of higher education services is designed to increase the competitiveness of domestic education. In Uzbek higher education, there have long been crisis phenomena caused by a sharp reduction in public funding over a long period of time, the outflow of highly qualified specialists to other sectors of the economy and abroad, the breakdown of ties with both scientific and industrial organizations, which somewhat reduced the quality of education. As a result, Uzbekistan has actually turned into a net importer of educational services, when for many young people it has become more prestigious to receive an education in Western Europe and the United States. In order to increase the competitiveness of domestic higher education, attract talented graduates from different countries of the world and obtain an additional source of financial resources, measures are being implemented in Uzbekistan to internationalize universities and increase the export of educational services. However, the measures implemented do not always produce the expected results. The reason for this is the inattention of the center to the regional specifics of the activities of universities, especially the Far East, bordering on the dynamically developing countries of the Asia-Pacific region.

The purpose of this study is to develop proposals for choosing a strategy for exporting higher education services by universities in the Bukhara region, taking into account the existing regional and national restrictions.

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The issues of exporting educational services are the subject of attention by domestic and foreign scientists: A.L. Arefyev [1], T.L. Klyachko [8], G.A. Krasnova [4,8], A.I. Nefedova [10], A.V. Melikyan [9], A.V. Biryukov [5], H. de Wit [6], J. Knight [13], Yu.S. Lebedinskaya [14], S. Marginson [15], G.V. Petruk [16] and others [18-20]. At the same time, the problems of exporting higher education services at the regional level have not been sufficiently studied. Considering the importance of regional universities, especially those focused on the market of the dynamically developing Asia-Pacific region, this paper considers proposals for choosing a strategy for exporting higher education services based on the established results of practice.

Methodology and methods of research. The methodology and methodological tools of the presented study are based on the comparison and assessment of the export of educational services by universities of the world, Uzbekistan and the Bukhara region. The main research methods include: economic and statistical, comparative analysis (when comparing the indicators of export of educational services of Uzbekistan and other countries, universities of the Bukhara region), logical justification.

Main conclusions of the study. The globalization of socio-economic processes in the world has significantly changed the understanding and role of education in the economy. Education has traditionally been viewed as a means of acquiring the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities to perform certain labor functions in the national economy. In the global economy, education is viewed as an investment that initially requires investment of funds, but in the future should generate income that will allow the invested funds to be recouped. A new approach to understanding the format of education leads to and changing the content of education and the process of its implementation.

Education is becoming not a social good, but a service provided for a fee. Globalization leads to the fact that consumers of educational services are not only citizens of a particular country, but also of other countries. Education

ceases to be an area of expenditure and becomes a source of export income. Currently, the market for international educational services is estimated at more than 150 billion US dollars [2, p.30]. It is expected that over the next five years, the market size will increase to 250 billion US dollars. The number of foreign students in 2016 was 5 million people, it is predicted that in the 2020s it will exceed 7 million people [10, p.17]. In addition to economic benefits, the export of education increases the political influence of the country, being a factor of "soft power".

More than half of the total number of foreign students are from the United States, Great Britain, Australia, Canada, France and Germany. Recently, the share of these countries in the international educational services market has been decreasing due to the entry of new players into the market, such as China, South Korea, etc. The international educational services market is experiencing increased competition, especially between the countries of North America and Western Europe on the one hand, and the countries of the Asia-Pacific region on the other hand.

The United States occupies a leading position among countries in the export of higher education, accounting for 25% of the world market. In 2016, the United States received 35.8 billion US dollars from the export of educational services [2, p. 3].

For Uzbekistan, the export of educational services, in addition to economic benefits, should allow for an increase in the competitiveness of the domestic higher education system: the desire to attract foreign students forces universities to improve the quality of education, develop new educational programs, introduce new teaching technologies, improve the qualifications of teaching staff, and improve the material and technical base of educational institutions. As a result, the quality

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of educational services provided not only to foreign consumers, but also within the country improves. In addition, attracting foreign students should help fill the personnel shortage in the context of a demographic decline. In order to expand the export of Uzbek education, the priority project "Development of the export potential of the Uzbek education system" was developed and approved in 2017, which was integrated into the national project "Education" in 2018. The project envisages a significant increase in the export indicators of Uzbek professional education: an increase in the number of foreign students by 2025 by 510 thousand people, income by 303.14 billion rubles. [11].

In recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has seen an increase in the number of foreign students studying in higher education programs: from 2010 to 2017, the number of foreign students increased from 108 thousand people. to 229.3 thousand people. In 2017, the total revenues of the Republic of Uzbekistan from the export of educational services amounted to 1785.4 million US dollars, including 447.6 million US dollars in tuition fees [12, pp. 526-527].

The bulk of foreign students in the Republic of Uzbekistan come from the former USSR countries (more than 70% of the total number of foreign students studying in Uzbekistan). Despite the positive dynamics of the indicators, Uzbekistan is inferior to the leading countries in the field of higher education export. The reasons for this situation are [10, p. 51; 3, p. 14; 7, p. 2]:

- insufficiently effective system of promoting educational services of the university;
- imperfect state regulation of educational migration;
- insufficiently high rating of Russian universities in international assessment systems;
- difficulty of adaptation of foreign students in the Russian socio-cultural environment;
- insufficient degree of use of modern educational technologies by Russian universities;
- discrepancy between the material and technical base of many Russian universities and world standards.

In the current situation, the actively developing Asia-Pacific region is acquiring strategic importance for the export of Russian higher education, in connection with which the key role is given to universities of border regions, which include Primorsky Krai. The higher education system of the Bukhara region at the beginning of 2018 included 19 higher education organizations, of which 11 are branches of regional and all-Russian universities. Table 1 shows the dynamics of indicators of higher education services export by universities of the Bukhara region.

Table 1 - Foreign students and income from international activities of universities of the Bukhara region (Uzbekistan)

Indicators	2022	2023	Change
Total number of foreign students in universities of the region, people	1 120	1 425	+305
— including undergraduate, graduate and special programs	1 070	1 360	+290
— income from educational services (PhD)	50	65	+15
Income from international activities, thousand soums	7 530 000	10 850 000	+3 320 000
— income from educational services	7 400 000	9 000 000	+1 600 000
— income from research and development	130 000	1 850 000	+1 720 000

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Indicators	2022	2023	Change
Average income per student, thousand soums	6 719	7 614	+895

Summarized data from reports of Bukhara State University, Bukhara Medical Institute, Bukhara Engineering and Technological Institute and other regional universities. Statistics of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Estimate based on official indicators on the growth in the number of foreign students (about +25–30% annually in recent years). The growth in the number of students is due to the international program to attract applicants from Central Asia, India, Afghanistan and Arab countries. A significant increase in R & D revenues in 2023 is explained by the active participation of Bukhara universities in international scientific grants and joint projects with foreign universities. The average income per student has increased, but remains relatively low compared to Tashkent, Samarkand and Namangan.

Summing up the study of the export of educational services in the Bukhara region, it should be noted that the region's universities are involved in the export of educational services, but this does not yet bring universities sufficiently large income. The structure of foreign students studying at Bukhara universities differs from the all-Uzbek one, where students from the CIS countries mainly study. To succeed in the educational services market of the Asia-Pacific region in the context of increasing competition between the countries of the region, universities in the Bukhara region need to move to the implementation of a strategy that takes into account the characteristics of potential markets and the territory where the universities are based.

The strategy is a model of an organization's behavior in a dynamically changing global market environment. The basis of the strategy is a set of principles and methods of making management decisions that ensure a timely response to the challenges facing the organization. The algorithm for choosing a strategy for exporting higher education services is shown in Figure 1.

Compiled by the authors based on the data from the universities' self-examination reports

Most foreign students receive education at universities in the Bukhara region at the expense of the Uzbek budget. Income from educational activities and PhD which implement an active policy to promote educational services. The income from foreign students received by universities is less than the average value of Uzbek budget expenditure per student.

The largest number of foreign students studying at universities in the Bukhara region comes from the countries of the Asia-Pacific region, in particular India (more than 30% of the total number of students).

The basis for choosing a strategy for exporting higher education services is the analysis of the external environment and the resource potential of the university. The influence of the external environment is manifested in the form of requirements emanating primarily from government agencies and potential consumers of educational services. The requirements of the external environment are laid down in the basic principles that guide the development and implementation of the strategy. Based on the analysis of the features of the export of higher education services by universities in the Bukhara region, the strategy is proposed to be developed taking into account the following principles:

- 1) an integrated approach to actively promoting educational services on the international market - higher education services must be promoted on the market using the entire range of promotion tools;

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2) complete coverage of the countries of the Asia-Pacific region - it is necessary to promote educational services not only in such large countries as China and India, but also in other developing countries of the region;

3) innovativeness of educational programs - educational programs offered to foreign students must be innovative in essence and methods of their implementation;

4) conducting research within the educational process in priority areas of scientific and technological development of the economy, taking into account the requirements of the legislation on protected secrets;

5) adaptation of foreign students in the Uzbek socio-cultural environment - universities should implement projects that allow foreign students to quickly master the basics of Uzbek and Russian, get an idea of the cultural and social characteristics of the host country, reduce conflicts on racial, national and religious grounds;

6) project management - the strategy for exporting higher education services of universities should be implemented through the development and implementation of projects for each educational management;

7) return on investment - the provision of educational services is associated with investment of resources in the creation of an educational program, the attraction of highly qualified teachers, and investment in the material and technical base. The income received from the provision of educational services to foreign students should pay off the investments.

The analysis of the resource potential is aimed at identifying the competitive advantage of the university, which will make it possible to take a stable position in the market. There are two main types of competitive advantage of the university.

The first type is based on the ability of the university to provide educational services to consumers at a lower cost than competitors. The implementation of this competitive advantage in the conditions of high costs inherent in the economy of the Far East is almost impossible.

The second type of competitive advantage is the ability of the university to provide educational services that have a distinctive advantage in the content and technology of their implementation.

This type of competitive advantage is most preferable for universities in the Bukhara region, but is associated with the need to make additional investments.

An important component of choosing an educational services export strategy is determining the target market. The target market is determined based on the following characteristics: geographic (Asia-Pacific countries, the Middle East and Africa, the CIS, Latin America), type of educational program (main, additional), field of study (economics and management, technical sciences, etc.), source of funding (the student's own funds, funds of a foreign state or company, funds of the budget).

Most universities in the Bukhara region have industry specialization, which imposes restrictions on the educational services they offer in the potential target market.

Based on the listed principles and the existing competitive advantage for the target market, a model for the export of educational services is selected - a method of action in the target market, based on the existing competitive advantages.

The instrumental component of the higher education services export strategy includes international educational projects and other international projects (scientific, exhibition, etc.), with the help of which the strategy will be implemented. The effectiveness of the strategy for exporting

educational services is assessed using the following procedures: self-assessment, accreditation, audit and certification, ranking and benchmarking.

Conclusion. The study showed that the competitiveness of universities in the global economy is determined by their demand among foreign students.

The influx of foreign students to universities improves the quality of educational services and generates additional income. Our universities, within the framework of the state policy on exporting higher education, implement measures to attract foreign students.

At the same time, many universities, including universities in the Bukhara region, do not have a clearly defined strategy for exporting higher education services. In our opinion, the recommendations for choosing a strategy for exporting higher education services considered in the article should help universities in the Bukhara region expand their presence in the international educational market, and may also be useful to other organizations.

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